

Progress in Highly Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Composites (TuFF)

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**CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS**

Celebrating 50 Years

History of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber (ADF)

- Short fibers (mm-scale)*
 - Aspect ratios 100-1000 typically
 - Easier to form
 - Filament level alignment creating dry aligned formats
 - Properties: modulus equivalent, strength ~50-80%
- Long Discontinuous (cm-scale)
 - Stretch Broken
 - Stochastic fiber length
 - Aspect Ratio 10k or greater
 - High forming forces
 - Properties match continuous

*Such, Matthew, Carwyn Ward, and Kevin Potter. "Aligned discontinuous fibre composites: a short history." *Journal of Multifunctional Composites* 2.3 (2014): 155-68.

What is TuFF?

TuFF is a feedstock with highly Aligned Discontinuous Fiber microstructure in tape, sheet and blank formats:

- Short fiber ($L/D \geq 600$), mm-scale
- Fiber agnostic (carbon (virgin and recycled), glass, ceramic, polymer and hybrids)
- Resin agnostic (TP's: PEI, LM-PAEK, PEKK; TS's: 977, 8552, Axiom)
- Filament level alignment control: $> 95\%$ ($\pm 5^\circ$)
- Aerospace quality and performance (FVF: $>57\%$)
- In-plane stretch enables stamp forming equivalent processes for high-rate production
- Enables recycling/upcycling of composites

TuFF Microstructure Parameters

Short Fiber Production

Fiber Diameter
Fiber Length

Polymer Coating

Polymer Viscosity

Fiber Alignment

Fiber End-to-End Gap
Fiber Orientation
Fiber Overlap

- What parameters are controlled?
 - Fiber Length and Diameter
 - Incoming Fiber Type
 - Fiber Alignment
 - Polymer Type
 - Fiber Volume Fraction
 - Interfacial adhesion
- Desirable stochastic parameters
 - Probability of multiple fiber ends at same location is low
 - Fiber end-to-end gap
 - Fiber overlap

Controlled TuFF Microstructure (Fiber Level) Necessary to Maximize Performance: $L/D > 600$, 95% within $\pm 5^\circ$, IFSS > 60 MPa

- Controlled fiber length (mm-range)
- Independent of fiber type
- Fiber Aspect Ratio (L/D) Criteria
 - Low Fiber Aspect Ratio (AR) for processing (square effect on viscosity)
 - Sufficient AR for 100% property translation

X-Ray CT of Quasi-isotropic Panel
Courtesy of ARL

TuFF Process – Fiber to Prepreg

Alignment Stage

- ~8 gsm per layer aligned dry preform

Stacking Stage

- 8 dry preforms (~60 gsm)
- 120 gsm dry stack with polymer film

Indexing Press

- Nominal 120 gsm prepreg (TP)
- Nominal 180 gsm prepreg (TS)

TuFF Integrated Manufacturing Facility

All TuFF Preforms, Prepreg (TP and TS), and blanks made at this site

Forming Cell (Spring 2020)

Installed Facility (DARPA-Effort)

ONR DURIP Forming Workcell
(Award N00014-19-1-2173)

UD-CCM's 9000 Sqft *TuFF* Integrated Manufacturing Facility (Funded by DARPA)

- Fibers to Parts under One Roof
 - Aligned dry preforms
 - Prepreg/blank production
 - Part forming
 - Forming characterization
- Equipment funded by DARPA, ONR DURIP and UD-CCM industrial gifts

From Short Fibers to Parts under One Roof

Science and Technology (S&T) Gaps

- What S&T gaps that need to be addressed for *TuFF* to be a viable material form for industry use?
 - Mechanics of highly-aligned short fiber composites
 - Property databases, allowables
 - Material stretch behavior and constitutive law for forming
 - Material stretch limits and effect on properties
 - Part manufacturing methods and guidelines
 - Repeatability from part to part
 - Modeling and Simulation tools
 - Part design
 - Process simulation

Progress from NASA-ULI Research Program

- ULI addresses S&T barriers in manufacturing of complex geometry composite parts for UAM and commercial air platforms
 - Meeting aerospace performance at automotive-like production rates
 - Transition technology to our industrial partners followed by the US industrial base
- Today's talk will cover progress in
 - Short fiber mechanics
 - Fatigue behavior of TuFF
 - Forming of TuFF
 - Tape steering enabled by TuFF

<https://www.ccm.udel.edu/research/program-highlights/nasa-university-leadership-initiative-uli/nasa-uli-presentation-request/>

Fiber Pullout Testing for Interface Properties

- High fiber/matrix Interface strength is critical for a high degree of property translation in ADF composites
- Pullout enables **easier visualization** of the failure modes on/at the interface
- Can test the interface in thermoset and thermoplastic materials
 - Ability to test at different **rates** and **temperatures**

Schematic of a pullout specimen

Interfacial Shear Strength & Traction Law

- IFSS >60 MPa is sufficient to obtain full translation of static properties with an aspect ratio of 600 for IM class carbon fibers
 - Based on *TuFF* IM7/PEI data
- For thermoplastics, carbon fibers are generally unsized but surface treated
 - Measured IFSS values are high (~60 to ~130 MPa) across the class of engineering thermoplastics evaluated
- Peak traction separation laws developed using FE models of the pullout experiments

Mechanical Properties: 3mm IM7/LM-PAEK, RTA

Autoclave laminate fabrication at the slow cooling rate (1-2 F/min to suppress wrinkles; Graphite caul plates; Void content < 1%

ASTM Test	TuFF IM7/LM PAEK					
	Laminate Detail	Modulus (Msi)	Strength (ksi)	Strain (%)	Poissons Ratio	FVF
Tension (3039)	[0] _n	21.6 (1.8%)	342 (5.8%)	1.53%	0.33	54%
	[90] _n	1.33 (0.7%)	15.33 (7%)	1.68%		56%
	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply	7.89 (2.9%)	118 (4.8%)	1.52%	0.33	55%
Compression (3410)	[90/0/90] ₅ , 120 gsm FAW per ply	6.93 (4.83%)	80 (8.97%)	1.29%		56%
	[45/0/-45/90] _{3s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply	7.19 (1.27%)	81.7 (4.16%)	1.22%		56%
In-Plane Shear (3518), 5% Strength	[45/-45] _{4s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply	0.73 (0.64%)	17.3 (1.15%)	>5%		
Short Beam Shear (2344)	[0] _n		15.38 (3.4%)			56%
Open Hole Tension (5766)	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply		58.6 (1.23%)			52%
Open Hole Compression (6484)	[45/0/-45/90] _{3s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply		46.4 (2.17%)			55%
Single-Shear Bearing (5961), Procedure A	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s} , 120 gsm FAW per ply		145 (3.8%)			55%

Mechanical Properties 3mm IM7/LM-PAEK

0 Tension

- Layup: $[0]_6$
- FVF: 54%
- Modulus: 21.6 msi (1.7%)
- Strength: 342 ksi (5.8%)
- Failure Strain: 1.53%

90 Tension

- Layup: $[90]_{16}$
- FVF: 56%
- Modulus: 1.33 ± 0.01 msi
- Strength: 15.33 ± 1.08 ksi
- Failure strain: 1.1-2%

SBS

- Layup: $[0]_{32}$
- FVF: 56%
- Strength: 15.38 ± 0.52 ksi

In-pane Shear

- Layup: $[45/-45]_{4s}$
- FVF: 55%
- Modulus: 0.73 ± 0.005 Msi
- Strength @ 5% strain: 17.33 ± 0.2 ksi
- Max strength: 25.74 ± 0.1 ksi
- Failure strain: >8%

Homogenous and
Low Void Content

Note: LM-PAEK had highest measured IFSS

Tension Fatigue of UD TuFF

- Utilizing an Instron 1331 hydraulic test frame
- Dual vision DIC system for optical strain measurements
 - Eliminate compliance factors in grips, hydraulic actuator, etc.
- Periodic static and dynamic measurements
 - Quasi-static modulus checks
 - Dynamic modulus checks

DIC: Modulus Check and Cyclic Strain

IR Camera: Temperature Checks

Normalized S/N Curve (semi-log) with TuFF [0]₄ and Comparison to Literature

- TuFF formats (IM7/PEI, IM7/LM-PAEK) tension fatigue in-line with literature for continuous.
 - Normalized S/N curves indicate IM7/PAEK TuFF having higher performance – higher interfacial bond strength
- S/N curve slope can be used to quantitatively compare strength reduction, however:
 - Dependent on matrix properties
 - Plasticity, toughness, cracking
 - Dependent on interfacial bonding
 - Dependent on fiber strength distribution

Tension Fatigue of [0/90/0] IM7/LM-PAEK TuFF Cross-Ply Laminate

- Laminates with 90 ply varying from 60-240 gsm
- IM7/LM-PAEK TuFF Fatigue testing at 0.9% strain
 - Thickest 240 gsm crossply laminate at 1.5 M cycles had NO transverse cracking
- Factors contributing to micro crack suppression:
 - High interface strength between the fiber and the resin (~129 MPa)
 - Higher resin toughness (>40% strain to failure for LM PAEK)
 - K_{1c}/G_{1c} is higher for LM-PAEK

Overall Approach for TuFF Forming

Modeling and Simulation

TuFF Material Model

Process Methodology

Process Input

Part Process Trials

TuFF/TS and TP Blanks in Model Geometries
Isothermal/Non-isothermal

validation

Actual Part Forming
Non-isothermal
At Rate

Formed Performance (ILT)

Establish process conditions based in ILT results

ADF Forming Limit Diagram Framework

Longitudinal Plane Strain

$$\epsilon_Z = -\epsilon_L$$

Longitudinal Uniaxial Tension

$$\epsilon_Z = \epsilon_T = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_L$$

$$\epsilon_Z = -\epsilon_L - \epsilon_T$$

Off axis strain will be a biaxial strain mode on this chart (ignoring shear)

Biaxial Strain

$$\epsilon_Z = -\epsilon_L - \epsilon_T$$

Transverse Plane Strain

$$\epsilon_Z = -\epsilon_T$$

- Failure mechanisms are material direction dependent
- FLD is constructed based on the material coordinates
 - Failure definitions *could* include:
 - Porosity / thickness uniformity constraints
 - Stiffness / Strength retention

TuFF (3mm IM7/PEI) Forming Limit Diagram

● Hemisphere:

◀▶ Cylinder

■ Flat Sheet

ONR DURIP Forming Characterization System

Equipment developed and acquired under
ONR DURIP Grant No. N00014-22-1-2124

Temperature: to 425 C
Clamp: 2-330 kN
Punch: 66 kN, 0-3 in/s
Bulge pressure: 300 psi

Forming Characterization
System : *Interlaken SP75*

*GOM ARAMIS
12MP DIC*

Plane Strain Gas Bulge Tool Set

Curvilinear Steering

- Constrained by Minimal Steering Radius (MSR)
- Continuous Fiber limited by inextensible fiber
- Defects (wrinkles/buckles at ID)

Paradigm Shift: Tuff in-situ stretch steering

- Local stretching allows to overcome MSR constraints
- Exploits extensibility in fiber direction
- 1-2 order of magnitude reduction in MSR without defects

Strain schematic

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{y}{r_c} + \epsilon_a \quad | \text{ Longitudinal strain field}$$

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{-w}{2r_c} + \epsilon_a \quad | \text{ Buckling critical}$$

$$\epsilon_o = \frac{w}{2r_c} + \epsilon_a \quad | \text{ Defect critical}$$

Process schematic

Minimum Steering Radius Comparison

- › Automated placement of tapes using Mikrosam (3mm IM7/PEI, 12.5mm wide tape)
- › 1-2 order of magnitude smaller steering radius compared to continuous fiber

A Statistical Approach to Establishing Stretch Steering Limits for Reducing Probability of Defects

- › The applied strain during stretch steering is bounded by
 - ID >0% (prevent buckling)
 - OD <43% (prevent defects)
- › Statistical analysis of the strain distributions based on stretched tape material variability
- › Process window limits probability of defect formation to 1%

Radius [mm] and distribution used [%]	Required strain (Bending formula) [%]	ID SF	Required strain with SF [%]	OD SF
100 (10%)	6.25	1.64	10.25	4.20
75 (10%)	8.33	1.48	12.33	3.49
50 (10%)	12.5	1.32	16.5	2.61
25 (40%)	25	1.4	35	1.23

$$\epsilon\left(\frac{W}{2}\right) = \epsilon_{ulim} = \epsilon_a + \frac{W}{2R_c} + z \sigma(\epsilon_{ulim})$$

$$\epsilon\left(-\frac{W}{2}\right) = \epsilon_{llim} = \epsilon_a - \frac{W}{2R_c} - z \sigma(\epsilon_{llim})$$

Summary

- TuFF is a highly-aligned ADF in prepreg format
 - Fiber and resin agnostic
 - Fiber to prepreg/blank and parts infrastructure established
- On-going research addressing S&T gaps for highly-aligned ADF composites
 - Short fiber mechanics – aspect ratio, IFSS, matrix vs property translation
 - Mechanical property assessments continuing (on-going programs)
 - Formability and material behavior vs temperature/strain rate
 - Forming process development and process variants
 - Recycled fiber converted to TuFF formats

Acknowledgements

- NASA-ULI Program
 - This work is funded by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration under Grant and Cooperative Agreement No. 80NSSC20M0164, issued through the Aeronautics Research Mission Directorate, Transformative Aeronautics Concepts Program, University Leadership Initiative.
 - Entire NASA-ULI Team

Session Talks

- Forming focus

- 9:35 AM - 9:55 AM Characterization and Modeling of Deformation Mechanisms of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Prepreg During Thermoforming, Aidan Ford - University of Delaware
- 9:55 AM - 10:15 AM Characterization and Modeling of Toolply and Plyply Friction of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Prepreg During Forming, Lauren Thomas - University of Delaware CCM
- 10:15 AM - 10:35 AM Modeling Transvers Shearing Viscosity and Material Tool Friction Interaction with Rectangular Squeeze Flow, Rafe GarciaHidalgo - University of Delaware
- 11:00 AM - 11:20 AM Stamp Forming of Highly Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Composite Blanks via Epoxy Matrix Staging, Matthew Abraham - University of Delaware
- 11:40 AM - 12:00 PM Tensile Behavior and Stress Relaxation of Uncured Prepreg of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Materials Constitutive Model Development for Stretch Forming, Navid Niknafs Kermani - University of Delaware

